

NEWSLETTER HYCOOL-IT

HYBRID COOLING & MANAGEMENT FOR IT INFRASTRUCTURES

WELCOME TO OUR SECOND HYCOOL-IT NEWSLETTER!

The [Hycool-IT EU Project](#) is working to develop a set of processes supported by both digital and technical equipment innovative solutions for an efficient and reliable development of IT Server Rooms for advanced tertiary buildings, with a special focus on its replicability through standardisation.

Hycool_IT has become an active member of the [SmartEnergyCluster](#), a collaborative effort of more than 20 EU projects focused on merging different energy services and incorporating non-energy benefits whilst overcoming market fragmentation and fostering cooperation. This inclusive approach bridges gaps and creates a common ground for business development across different segments.

As part of the efforts to make the project known and to generate synergies with similar projects Hycool_IT as joined the 2cool2waste cluster. The cluster fosters synergies in:

- Knowledge sharing through joint events, publications, and outreach
- Waste heat recovery and reuse
- Electrification of thermal systems
- High-efficiency solutions for buildings and industry

The cluster will held its first webinar on the 2nd October and Hycool_It will be presented by project coordinator in a talk with the title: “Hycool-it: waste heat from server room in tertiary buildings – A case study”. More details will follow on social media in the coming weeks. Follow us for this and more interesting content.

LET'S TAKE A LOOK AT WHAT OUR PROJECT HAS BEEN DOING!

Redesign of 100 kW server room cooling system with more efficient chillers and waste heat reuse.

The renovation is based on the following efficiency drivers:

- New CHillers with Intelligent free cooling and higher seasonal efficiency
- In-ROW server COOLERS with higher effectiveness TO RAISE chilled water temperature
- Heat exchanger to USE SERVER WASTE HEAT as THE heat Source for a new, HEAT PUMP BASED, heating system in A university BUILDING

The new solution optimizes energy consumption, lowering at the same time electricity consumption for IT equipment cooling and natural gas consumption for space heating.

Digital Twin platform for simulation model tracking and software in the loop control optimization

The architecture is bases on standard ISO 23247-2 and the ISO 19650 and consists of the following layers:

- Physical (architecture envelope and server room)
- MEP, sensors and control systems - data centre components – controlled objects
- Monitored data
- Digital services (Optimized Simulation, SIMBOTS and Model Predictive Control)

The integrated ecosystem called the simulation model tracking system – SMTS, now ready to be deployed in beta testing

PROJECT NEWS

Hycool_IT third general assembly in Belgrade

On the 20th and 21st May consortium members gathered in Belgrade at the Institute Mihajlo Pupin to celebrate the third general assembly. The meeting started with a technical discussion on the Requirements and methodology definition.

[▶ Learn More](#)

Hycool_IT at SmartWins Polimi Scientific Workshop

SmartWins in conjunction with POLIMI held a scientific workshop on digital twins. It was held at POLIMI premises in Milan on the 20th and 21st March. The workshop was oriented to the scientific community and industry.

[▶ Learn More](#)

Hycool_IT at PDP 2025

From March 12th to 14th, Pablo Vicente Legazpi, Project Manager at Building Digital Twin Association, attended the Euromicro International Conference on Parallel, Distributed, and Network-Based Processing (PDP 2025) hosted by Università degli Studi di Torino.

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Hycool_IT at SmartWins workshop

The Scientific workshop *Introduction to Digital Twin Technology and Sustainable Energy Management* was held 5th of December in an event in Berlin organized by SmartWins under the frame of the Boosting Research for a Smart and Carbon Neutral Built Environment with Digital Twins. Rossano Scoccia from Politecnico de Milano attended the meeting and make a presentation on Hycool_IT.

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Hycool_IT at 10th Rehva Summit

On the 19th of November took place the 10th Rehva Summit at Brussels. Participation of the BDTA. Participation of the BDTA was to have more links with this federation of associations along EU. The future dynamic energy performance and certified mathematical models.

[▶ Learn More](#)

Hycool_IT at the Digital Twins and Mathematical Simulation event in Madrid

Great event the 14th of November in Madrid about Digital TWins and Mathematical Simulation, presenting the Hycool-IT EU Project to the audience. Some presentations were especially interesting, like the ones from CERN (Benjamin Sadu, Brad Schofield), European Space Agency – ESA (Remko Moeys) and Cesar De Prada (Universidad de Valladolid). Thank you to EAG (Empresarios Agrupados – GHESA) for the great organization.

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